

**The Movement of Binary Star Systems and Stars in Galaxies and a Novel Explanation:
Complex Gravitation**

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Abstract

Here, we discuss the literature regarding the roles of stellar mass, dark energy, and gravity in the rotation of galaxies and binary star systems. Furthermore, a novel explanation for the movement of stars in galaxies as well as for the movement of stars in binary star systems, called complex gravitation, is introduced here. In addition, a slightly modified law of gravitation is described.

Review: The Movement of Binary Star Systems and Stars in Galaxies

I. Summary

A recent study by Chae [1] investigated a gravitational anomaly in the orbital dynamics of wide binary stars under conditions of weak gravitational acceleration. The orbital motions of these binary stars are analyzed using data from the Gaia DR3 database, revealing deviations from the expected Newtonian range at accelerations below 10^{-9} m/s². These deviations indicate that gravity behaves differently under specific acceleration conditions. The study also compares these observations with predictions made in quadratic Lagrangian (AQUAL) theory, noting a significant 10σ deviation from the Newtonian expectation at $g_N = 10^{-10.15}$ m/s², where the observed Newton-predicted acceleration ratio is 1.43 with a deviation of 0.06. These findings suggest that standard gravity does not fully explain the dynamics of wide binary star motion, especially at low accelerations, necessitating the proposal and empirical evaluation of novel theories to account for these observations.

II. Systematic Review

McGaugh [2] reviews previous predictions regarding the motion dynamics of rotating galaxies, with a focus on modified Newtonian dynamics (MOND) data corroborated in numerous previous studies. From his observations, three main categories emerge: proven MOND predictions, galaxies mimicking MOND behaviors, and novel, unexplored aspects of binary star system motion. These data also highlight the presence of dark matter. Feng [3] and Vitral [4] argue that the absence of visible mass providing gravitational support for the orbital velocity of matter in rotating disk galaxies is evidence of nonbaryonic dark matter. Newton's laws are used

to determine the mass distribution in rotating galaxies, as they form closed systems subject to the universal laws of physics.

According to Arcones and Thielemann [8], all elements in the universe originate from cosmic events such as the Big Bang and stellar explosions. These authors assess early papers on nucleosynthesis and related nuclear physics processes, which, depending on conditions such as temperature, density, pressure, and neutron/proton ratios, produce elements such as lead, lithium, and other rare earth metals. Arcones and Thielemann [8] aim to enhance our understanding of astrophysical models by improving existing stellar system representations, analyzing the composition of ejecta from stellar winds, exploring supernova core collapse mechanisms, and examining the energy transition into hypernova and bursts of gamma radiation. According to this study, nova explosions result from combinations of stellar systems, X-rays, type 1a supernovae, and mergers between black holes and neutron stars, leading to the ejection of materials rich in rare metals, often in isotopic form, which become integral to the formation of future stars.

As low-mass and intermediate-mass stars, including those in binary systems, transition to the asymptotic giant branch, they become complex cosmic objects whose mechanisms depend on various kinematic processes [10-12]. New chemical elements are formed, leading to reactions that contribute to the creation of other novel components [12]. Dust grains form in the upper atmospheres of stellar objects, resulting in accelerated winds that scatter photons through gas collisions, aided by the bodies' angular momenta. Despite the abundance of chemical elements and other forms of mass in the universe, dark matter and dark energy also constitute a significant portion of the universe. Elbeze [13] reports that observations of the rotation curve of galaxies on a flat plane can only be explained by the existence of dark energy in the cosmos. Applying Newton's laws and the theory of gravitation in such cases, with the Hubble constant as a limit,

reveals the presence of an unaccounted-for spacetime variable, E_0 , which may represent dark energy. This view builds upon Elbeze's [14] earlier work and is supported by Riess [15].

In the July issue of *The Astrophysical Journal*, an article was published on the mathematical description of binary star systems by Kyu-Hyun Chae [1].

A significant number of binary star systems have been newly discovered with the Gaia telescope. Importantly, data on the movements of these binary star systems are also now available.

Chae notes that the movements of binary star systems and the rotations of stars in galaxies cannot be described using the classic Kepler approach.

Compared to what is indicated by Kepler's approach, binary star systems have a mean acceleration that is too high by a factor of 1.4 on average. The article postulates that one should instead choose the Milgrom approach.

In the Milgrom approach, also called the MOND approach, Newton's acceleration law is slightly modified. Building on this concept, it should be noted that the MOND approach is not the only way to solve the problem by slightly modifying a physical law. Here, it is suggested that not only Newton's law of acceleration but also Newton's law of gravitation should be slightly modified. Specifically, Newton's law of gravitation and Coulomb's law of electricity can be unified into a common law that uniformly describes the attractive properties of both gravity and electricity in terms of a complex quantity. This view is not a complication but rather a simplification of the problem. Electricity is stronger than gravity by a factor of $b=10^{10}$. It follows that in such a unified description, nothing changes when considering small masses. The newly created mass–

charge interactions only become relevant when considering large masses on the order of $1E10$ kg.

A simple calculation shows that the deviation of the movement of binary star systems described in the cited article can be easily explained to within an order of magnitude.

With the appropriate choice of units, the following law applies, which we call “complex gravitation”:

$Mass1 * mass2 + mass1 * charge2 + charge1 * mass2 + charge1 * charge2 = 1.4 \text{ times the force}$

$$1 + 1 * x + x * 1 + x^2 = 1.4$$

This means that for charges of 0.225 Coulomb and 1.77 Coulomb, there is already a deviation in force and acceleration by a factor of 1.4.

For a star that is heavier than $1E10$ kg, a corresponding deviation will occur only with a correspondingly higher charge. It is therefore quite easy to explain the deviation in acceleration in binary star systems described in the cited article if one starts from a unified complex law of gravity and electricity.

Moreover, it is not necessary to assume exceptionally high charges. Even small charges are sufficient. It is only important that these charges exist between the two stars and are not completely compensated.

III. Conclusion

Chae's [1] study illustrates the inability of standard gravity to account for the motion dynamics of wide binary stars, especially at low accelerations. The present paper also includes a systematic literature review to highlight the roles of stellar mass, gravity, and dark energy in the rotation of binary star systems and galaxies. The key conclusion of this analysis is that novel theories are needed to sufficiently account for these observations.

Furthermore, it is proposed that complex gravitation can serve as an alternative explanation for the differences between Newton's laws and the observations of binary star movements. In this regard, complex gravitation is similar to the MOND theory.

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Table 1

Table 1: Experimental results

Reference number	Experimental results
Part A: Movement of binary stars	
[11]	Emission maps from the IRC+10216 star, examined under the IRAM 30 m telescope, show the presence of dense spherical structures. The data collected in this study show that the central star, known as CW Leo, emits a lot of carbon (II) oxide gas, with the higher emissions occurring at the nucleus. This phenomenon, according to the authors, is caused by photodissociation. All astronomical models created and used in this study are in line with Newton.
[12]	The authors observed 20 OH/IR stars within the Milky Way Galaxy with the Nancay radio telescope. The results show these stars have variable emissions, and this data was used to compute the phase lag of each star based on the outflow of materials from their surrounding shells. While ongoing observation and data collection continue to refine current knowledge about these systems, existing data have high uncertainties exceeding 20%. The approach proposed in this study (phase lag) offers a way to determine distances between Earth and stars in the Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB) characterized by dense outer layers. AGB describes an evolutionary stellar period for low- to medium-mass stars

	<p>approaching the ends of their lives. They turn into red giants with luminosity several thousand times greater than the Sun's. Most AGB stars with dense outer layers are in line with Newton but some display altered characteristics.</p>
<p>Part B: Movement of stars in galaxies</p>	
[1]	<p>A gravitational anomaly has been discovered where gravitational acceleration (g_N) is significantly weak with data less than 10^{-9} m/s^2. This data was obtained from an analysis of wide binary star dynamics in the Gaia DR3 database. This study's findings are in line with MOND.</p>
[4]	<p>This paper involved an analysis of the core collapse of a star and resultant tidal interactions and mass segregation. It modeled globular clusters using simulations built from data collected by the Hubble Space Telescope and the Gaia astrometric mission. The results point to the existence of a dark matter mini-halo.</p>
[5]	<p>The authors of this study investigated the effect of angular momentum on various galaxies using kinematic data from early-type variants. The findings showed that the rotation of the outer region of these galaxies (halo spin) does not account for the observable differences in the properties of spiral galaxies. However, the data supported scenarios in which these galaxies would preserve a portion of their initial energies (10-60%) during the expansion process. These findings are in line with Newton.</p>
[6]	<p>The authors of this study discovered a pattern showing that elliptical and spiral galaxies follow the paths predetermined by their angular momenta and mass. This process was described to be similar to the Tully Fisher relation. The authors</p>

	<p>found that elliptical galaxies are shaped based on their mass, size, and rotation properties. This phenomenon is known as the mass-size-rotation conspiracy.</p> <p>These findings challenge earlier theories based on the idea that elliptical galaxies accumulate their angular momenta during mergers. These findings are in line with Newton.</p>
[7]	<p>According to this study, the turbulent motions observed in most galaxies are consistent with the Toomre instability parameter ($Q = 1$). This value associates a galaxy's motion with the critical gravitational disk instability threshold.</p> <p>Therefore, instability is a significant factor in the occurrence of turbulence within galactic formations. These findings are in line with Newton.</p>
[9]	<p>Stars on the asymptotic giant branch experience a mass loss due to gravity-related factors, especially in the wind-forming regions. The findings of this study are in line with Newton.</p>
[10]	<p>Inner winds are a characteristic of the motion dynamics of the asymptotic giant branch. There are four parent molecules in the four objects, indicating that these chemical species form at random stages of the evolution of asymptotic giant branch galaxies. This study focuses on the chemical aspect of the universe, but all physics-related computations, assertions, and findings are in line with Newton.</p>
Part C: Dark matter, dark energy, and their effects on galactic rotation	
[2]	<p>MOND data confirms the motion dynamics of rotating galaxies. Post hoc explanations for observations in terms of dark matter are possible in this case;</p>

	hence, the data is reliable. These findings can be used to predict mass loss in galaxies as well. The findings of this study are in line with MOND.
[3]	Solving a force balance equation based on Newton's laws from measured rotation curves is the most reliable method for determining the distribution of mass in rotating disk galaxies. The findings of this study are in line with Newton.
[14]	According to the authors, Hubble's constant is not affected by dark energy and dark matter. Additionally, the most cited evidence for nonbaryonic dark matter is the apparent lack of visible mass offering gravitational support to the observed orbital velocity of matter in rotating disk galaxies. The findings of this study are in line with Newton.
Part D: The role of universal constants, chemical formation, and electromagnetic factors in star system dynamics	
[8]	All elements in the universe are formed from the Big Bang, stellar explosions, and other cosmic events. Most heavy atoms were formed from the nucleosynthesis of supernovae. This study is in line with Newton.
[13]	According to this study, gravitomagnetism causes planets to generate heat in their cores. Additionally, Earth is currently in a phase of thermal balance. This study is in line with Newton.
[15]	Observations from the Hubble Space Telescope confirm the Hubble constant to be 2.4%. Near-infrared observations of Cepheid variables were leveraged to achieve the improvement from an initial value of 3.3%. This study's findings are in line with Newton.

I. Key Findings

Table 2: Key findings

Reference number	Key findings
Part A: Movement of binary stars	
[11]	<p>Changes in the density of shells around stars and galaxies reveal a gradual loss of mass, which affects their rotational dynamics over time. As these formations evolve, the expansion of carbon (II) oxide envelopes fills the voids left behind by the lost mass. This research offers great insights into the formation and mobility of galaxies and stars despite not precisely explaining the dynamics involved.</p> <p>This paper is in line with Newton.</p>
[12]	<p>The paper presents the phase-lag approach and how it can be used to estimate distances from Earth to stars in the Asymptotic Giant Branch. It focuses on stars with optically thick circumstellar shells. The phase lag of stars satisfying this condition (20 OH/IR) in the galactic disk has been determined based on a monitoring program with the Nancay radio telescope. The findings offer great insight into galactic dynamics, but their accuracy cannot be established since the study is ongoing. Most AGB stars with dense outer layers conform to Newton but some do not.</p>
Part B: Movement of stars in galaxies	
[1]	<p>Wide binary star systems with weak gravitational acceleration often have predictable orbital dynamics following Newtonian physics. However, based on the observations of this study, the correlation between acceleration and other</p>

	properties consistently diverges from expectation. For instance, the findings showed a deviation of 0.007 from the expected results, translating to a statistical significance of 10 sigma. Despite these slight deviations, this study was in line with MOND.
[4]	The thesis improved current data modeling standards in the construction of galactic density profiles, motion measurements, and Jeans kinematic modeling. It also highlighted new constraints to consider when computing globular cluster formations, such as the dark matter mini-halo. This study is in line with Newton.
[5]	The paper established the role of angular momentum in the physical mechanisms of the evolution of j^* and m^* galaxies, involving outflows, stripping, collapse bias, and merging processes. The vector sum of these processes, according to the results, matches the observations made. Based on these results, this study is in line with Newton.
[6]	In early-type galaxies, there are observable links between the angular momentum of stars. However, spiral galaxies of the same mass have higher angular momenta than their elliptical counterparts, often as much as 4:1 and 3:1. The results of this study are in line with Newton.
[7]	Baryon fraction, angular momentum, and pressure create turbulence. However, the resultant kinematics need to satisfy the Toomre instability parameter of 1 to be considered a major driver of galactic turbulence. These findings are in line with Newton.
[9]	Stars within the asymptotic giant branch experience mass loss due to factors

	<p>related to gravity. In the case of galaxies, their rotational mechanics and dynamics lead to gradual mass shedding, especially in the wind-forming regions. These findings are in line with Newton.</p>
[10]	<p>Observations of key molecules in stars in the asymptotic giant branch, at both low and high excitation levels, were carried out using APEX and JCMT telescopes at millimeter and submillimeter wavelengths. These observations showed that the inner winds of stars in the asymptotic giant branch are based on nonequilibrium chemistry, showing these regions have a chemical imbalance. These results are in line with Newton.</p>
Part C: Dark matter, dark energy, and their effects on galactic rotation	
[2]	<p>MOND data confirms the motion dynamics of rotating galaxies. Post hoc explanations for observations in terms of dark matter are possible in this case; hence, the data is reliable. These findings can be used to predict mass loss in galaxies as well. These findings are in line with MOND.</p>
[3]	<p>The most dependable and accurate method for estimating the distribution of mass within rotating disc galaxies is the solution of a force balance equation derived from Newton's laws of motion applied to galactic rotation curves. The approach proposed by these authors, therefore, is in line with Newton.</p>
[14]	<p>Hubble's constant is not affected by dark energy and dark matter. Additionally, the most cited evidence for nonbaryonic dark matter is the apparent lack of visible mass offering gravitational support to the observed orbital velocity of matter in rotating disk galaxies. The findings of this paper are in line with</p>

	Newton.
Part D: The role of universal constants, chemical formation, and electromagnetic factors in star system dynamics	
[8]	All elements in the universe are formed from the Big Bang, stellar explosions, and other cosmic events. Most heavy atoms were formed from the nucleosynthesis of supernovae. All computations and findings in this paper are in line with Newton.
[13]	Rocky planets such as Earth depend on gravitomagnetics to generate heat in their cores. Based on current data, the Earth is in a phase of thermal balance. These findings are in line with Newton.
[15]	Observations from the Hubble Space Telescope confirm the Hubble constant to be 2.4%. Near-infrared observations of Cepheid variables were leveraged to achieve the improvement from an initial value of 3.3%. The computations and observations that were used to arrive at these figures are in line with Newton.